

Metabolite identification studies and their role in the drug discovery and development process

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Abstract

Identification of metabolites may be one of the most time-consuming steps during the drug discovery and development process. Recent progress in analytical methods e.g. liquid chromatography (LC) and mass spectrometry (MS) enables such studies to be performed at an early stage and continues over the whole drug development process.

At the early drug discovery stage, the metabolite identification studies help to identify the metabolic “soft-spots” of molecules and thus guide the chemistry program in order to optimize high clearance compounds to more stable candidate drugs (CD). Additionally, such studies elucidate the individual variability in metabolism which often help to explain variations in candidate drug response.

The outcome of the metabolite identification studies is also detection of metabolites that could be pharmacologically active and contribute to the efficacy of the CD, for IP protection, but also detection of compounds that form reactive intermediates and/or toxic metabolites that could cause adverse effects. Such information is critical to have at an early stage for a successful drug discovery program.

The Metabolite in Safety Testing (MIST) guidance describes how the metabolites should be tested and compared between the species used in the toxicological studies and human. Thus, the metabolite identification studies are also important to select and justify animal species used in toxicological studies.

Finally, animal and human mass balance studies performed using the ¹⁴C-label should confirm and explain any items related to metabolism and elimination of the drug.

In this contribution, we would like to describe the principles and recent strategies used for metabolite identification studies in vitro, early in the drug discovery and development process.